

ANN Based Model Development for Material Removal Rate in Dry Turning in Indian Context

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Abstract : This paper is intended to develop an artificial neural network (ANN) based model of material removal rate (MRR) in the turning of ferrous and nonferrous material in a Indian small scale industry. MRR of the formulated model was proved with the testing data and artificial neural network (ANN) model was developed for the analysis and prediction of the relationship between inputs and output parameters during the turning of ferrous and nonferrous materials. The input parameters of this model are operator, workpiece, cutting process, cutting tool, machine and the environment. The ANN model consists of a three layered feedforward back propagation neural network. The network is trained with pairs of inputs/outputs datasets generated when machining ferrous and nonferrous material. A very good performance of the neural network, in terms of agreement with experimental data, was achieved. The model can be used for the analysis and prediction of the complex relationship between dependent and the independent parameters in turning operations.

Keywords : Field data based model, Artificial neural network, Simulation, Convectional Turning, Material removal rate.

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